

CORRECTIONS CAREERS

EUROPEAN CAREER COUNSELLING GUIDELINES
FOR STAFF WORKING
IN CRIMINAL CORRECTIONAL JUSTICE SYSTEM

WP3

**STAKEHOLDERS ANALYSIS
IN CCJ CAREERS,
THE SUPPORTIVE COMPETENCIES,
AND EDUCATIVE NEEDS**

Co-funded by the
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CONTENT

Purpose	4
Third Stakeholder checkpoint for Driver Mapping and Axes of Uncertainties in career management competencies within CCJ -- aggregated results	3
Preparation of the activities	3
Topics of the Meetings	3
Organisers	3
Participants	3
Results	3
Political Factors	3
Economic Factors	3
Societal Factors	3
Technological Factors	3
Legislative Factors	3
Environmental Factors	3
Conclusion	3
4th Stakeholder check point for a DACUM validation of the competencies profile – aggregated results	3
Description of the events	3
Participants	3
Results	3
Prison Officers	3
Prison Educators	3
Probation Counsellor	3
Psychologists	3
Main Findings	3
References	3

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TABLE INDEX

Table 1. 3rd Stakeholder Checkpoint – Data Collection Strategy by partner	4
Table 2. 4th Stakeholder Checkpoint - Data Collection Strategy by partner	2
Table 3. Aggregated results on duties, tasks, competencies, behaviours and knowledge – prison officers	3
Table 4. Aggregated results on challenges, future skills/competencies/behaviours/training – prison officers	3
Table 5. Aggregated results on duties, tasks, competencies, behaviours and knowledge – prison educators	3
Table 6. Aggregated results on challenges, future skills/competencies/behaviours/training – prison educators	3
Table 7. Aggregated results on duties, tasks, competencies, behaviours and knowledge – probation counsellor	3
Table 8. Aggregated results on challenges, future skills/competencies/behaviours/training – probation counsellour	3
Table 9. Aggregated results on duties, tasks, competencies, behaviours and knowledge – psychologists	3
Table 10. Aggregated results on challenges, future skills/competencies/behaviours/training - psychologists	3

TABLE INDEX

Figure 1. Areas of training identified	4
Figure 2. Soft skills identified as in need of training	2
Figure 3. Specific procedures identified as in need of training	3

CORRECTIONS CAREERS

CONTENT

Purpose	4
Third Stakeholder checkpoint for Driver Mapping and Axes of Uncertainties in career management competencies within CCJ -- aggregated results	3
Preparation of the activities	3
Topics of the Meetings	3
Organisers	3
Participants	3
Results	3
Political Factors	3
Economic Factors	3
Societal Factors	3
Technological Factors	3
Legislative Factors	3
Environmental Factors	3
Conclusion	3
4th Stakeholder check point for a DACUM validation of the competencies profile – aggregated results	3
Description of the events	3
Participants	3
Results	3
Prison Officers	3
Prison Educators	3
Probation Counsellor	3
Psychologists	3
Main Findings	3
References	3

CORRECTIONS CAREERS

TABLE INDEX

Table 1. 3rd Stakeholder Checkpoint – Data Collection Strategy by partner	4
Table 2. 4th Stakeholder Checkpoint - Data Collection Strategy by partner	2
Table 3. Aggregated results on duties, tasks, competencies, behaviours and knowledge – prison officers	3
Table 4. Aggregated results on challenges, future skills/competencies/behaviours/training – prison officers	3
Table 5. Aggregated results on duties, tasks, competencies, behaviours and knowledge – prison educators	3
Table 6. Aggregated results on challenges, future skills/competencies/behaviours/training – prison educators	3
Table 7. Aggregated results on duties, tasks, competencies, behaviours and knowledge – probation counsellor	3
Table 8. Aggregated results on challenges, future skills/competencies/behaviours/training – probation counsellour	3
Table 9. Aggregated results on duties, tasks, competencies, behaviours and knowledge – psychologists	3
Table 10. Aggregated results on challenges, future skills/competencies/behaviours/training - psychologists	3

TABLE INDEX

Figure 1. Areas of training identified	4
Figure 2. Soft skills identified as in need of training	2
Figure 3. Specific procedures identified as in need of training	3

FINAL REPORT

PURPOSE

This final report comprehends the results obtained by the CCJ4C partnership concerning the stakeholders' analysis in CCJ Careers. Each partner aimed to analyse the needs and characteristics of the correctional staff in their country to provide in-depth knowledge of this specific target group. In particular, their learning and training situations, effective methodologies, and understanding of the skills set needed to manage their careers. This Working Package aims the development a catalogue of skills in CCJ careers.

THIRD STAKEHOLDER CHECKPOINT FOR DRIVER MAPPING AND AXES OF UNCERTAINTIES IN CAREER MANAGEMENT COMPETENCIES WITHIN CCJ - AGGREGATED RESULTS

PREPARATION OF THE ACTIVITIES

In the stage of preparation for the workshops, each partner invited potential stakeholders interested in participating. Some partners also disseminated the event through their social pages (e.g., LinkedIn) to reach a broader range of correctional staff.

The workshops took place on the following dates and locations:

PARTNER	DATE	LOCATION
SNPP - National Union of Prison Workers, Romania	15 th July 2021	Bucharest's Union Plaza Hotel
Timisoara Prison, Romania	23 rd July 2021	Zoom platform
CEIPES - Centro Internazionale per la Promozione dell'Educazione e lo Sviluppo, Italy	27 th July 2021 from 16:00 to 18:30	Bucharest's Union Plaza Hotel
IPS_Innovative Prison Systems, Portugal	23 rd and 29 th June 2021 from 10:00 to 12:00 from 15:00 to 17:00	Zoom platform
YA - York Associates International, United Kingdom	02-30 th August 2021	Online
BrainLog, Denmark	22 nd October 2021 from 9:30 to 11:00 a.m	Zoom platform

Table 1. 3rd Stakeholder Checkpoint – Data Collection Strategy by partner

All partners contacted the participants previously to provide the agenda and the access link/location of the activity. It is also noteworthy that most of the partners organised the workshop in an online format due to the current COVID-19 pandemic restrictions.

Also, due to multiple constraints (including the COVID-19 pandemic, the summer holiday period, and low staffing issues within the participants' workplaces), York Associates could not gather all stakeholders together for one meeting on this occasion. Therefore, their checkpoint was carried out using a mix of focus group discussions, one-on-one meetings, telephone interviews and email interviews. Some of the data gathered by the York Associates was obtained during previous stakeholder focus groups.

TOPICS OF THE MEETINGS

The subject/topic of all the meetings involves the relevant stakeholders looking at how career management competencies are built and used, the future needs, the drivers that trigger change, and the significant uncertainties.

Driver Mapping is used to identify the Political, Economic, Societal, Technological, Legislative, and Environmental drivers (PESTLE) shaping CCJ career management's future environment and the needed competencies to navigate it.

This approach aims to identify the two most important driving forces, i.e., those very uncertain developments (and therefore can develop into different directions) and could have a decisive impact on CCJ careers. In other words, driving forces, which serve as scenario axes (Axes of Uncertainty), are those developments that score on both indicators' uncertainty' and 'impact' (Klooster & Asselt, 2006).

It is assumed that this technique, being a frame that the different actors share, fosters convergent action among many actors, despite the diverse and often conflicting data that these practitioners are confronted with.

ORGANISERS

The CEIPES focus group was organised by the project manager Silvia Calcavecchio, responsible for the CCJ4C project on behalf of CEIPES and by the head of the CEIPES employment agency Giuseppe Tredici, as an expert in identifying professional skills in different work fields, with experience in the sector relating to organisational well-being in contexts close to the police.

Ângela Fernandes was the person within IPS that delivered the workshops. Ângela Fernandes is a psychotherapist and a forensic expert. She holds a master's degree in Psychology and a PhD in Applied Psychology from the University of Minho, Portugal. Within IPS, Ângela Fernandes is assigned to the Rehabilitation and Reintegration portfolio, under which she collaborates in several projects.

On behalf of the York Associates, the checkpoint lead was Tom Flaherty, and the checkpoint administrator was Linda Simi.

Regarding the Timisoara Prison, the welcome speech of the workshop was delivered by Mrs Cristina Busuioc from Timisoara Prison. Then, Mrs Bogdan Ionuț Nicolescu presented a PowerPoint document about the CCJ4C project. He delivered information about the

partnership, project objectives and activities. The next presentation was about Driver Mapping and Axes of Uncertainty techniques presented by Valentin Dorin Zaharia. He explained the workshop's strategy and context as the third "stakeholder's checkpoint". Valentin underlined that the goal of this workshop is to develop, test, and establish working methodologies to improve the career guidance process in criminal justice, emphasising the skills needed to manage one's career.

Concerning BrainLog, the focus group interview was organised by its CEO, Martin Savchev, the CCJ4C project manager, on behalf of BrainLog.

PARTICIPANTS

Various personalities involved in the course of the project were invited to the focus groups. SNPP reunited 18 participants, namely NTP team members; National Administration of Penitentiaries (Director of Human Resources Directorate, Head of Education Service, Cooperation and Programs officer); National Trade Union of Prison Policemen: Local Trade Union Leaders; Prison units: prison policemen; the University of Bucharest –Psychology Faculty; Research Institutes: Quality of Life Research Institute; and other trade unions: Publishing representative.

Penitenciarul Timisoara brought together 28 representatives of Timisoara Prison; National Union of Prison Police; Romanian National Administration of Prison; Educative Center Buzias; Arad Prison; Oradea Prison; International Police Association-region 6; Romanian Centre for Penitentiary Studies; West University Timisoara; Evaluator expert; Career Counseling and Guidance Center; West University Timisoara; and Baia Mare Prison.

CEIPES reunified the President of UIL trade union for Sicily region; Correctional police inspector and member of the UIL trade union; President of UIL trade union for Tuscany region; and Functionary of INAPP Erasmus Plus agency.

IPS gathered 4 participants, such as Chief of guards, educators/human resources, deputy Director and Prison Guards.

The York Associates brought together 9 participants, namely Prison officer in a maximum-security facility, with 12 months of service; Prison officer in a maximum-security facility, with 3.5 years' service; Head of Learning & Skills for HM Prison Service; Youth Offending Officer in Restorative Justice team, with 6.5 years' service; Member of the UK Independent Prisons Monitoring Board; Director of an organisation working on creative learning programmes inside prisons; Lecturer of Criminology; University Deputy Dean of School of Education and Social Sciences, formerly Principal Lecturer of Criminology; The

In this context, it is also essential that the Italian participants consider that the reality of the Italian prison population is peculiar due to the Mafia criminals, which should be addressed.

ECONOMIC FACTORS

The budget is a concern shared by the diverse participants. They all agree that prison administrations are underfinanced, and this is reflected in various aspects:

- Correctional officers' income is low, and there is no appropriate reward system.
- Working conditions – precarious; endowments/equipment are old and improper.
- Training activities are scarce and of poor quality.

These aspects, more directly or indirectly, impact other variables, such as:

- A correctional officer is not an attractive role and is not perceived positively. Hence, there are few renewed staff, and the old ones are retiring or need sick leaves.
- The job risks are not compensated – severe mental and physical harm dangers.
- Prison overcrowding.

It is considered that financial resources should be used to fulfil these concerns, alongside training for both prison staff and inmates. In fact, the development of workers is necessary from an economic point of view, essentially because:

- a) without adequate training and learning, the quality of work will most likely be poor/unsatisfactory, and;
- b) they hold a position that can pose a risk and should be compensated and motivated. Furthermore, participants consider that re-educating and teaching professionals is also fundamental for inmates' progress because they would be capacitated with more adequate skills and competencies to perform their duties better.

The participants shared concern regarding **the degradation of physical conditions** and have identified it as a primary challenge, as prisons' hygiene and health conditions are deplorable.

SOCIETAL FACTORS

One of the factors highly identified is grounded on the **stigmatisation of the profession** itself. Participants believe that society built an image of correctional officers that is far from the truth. For instance, the history of the job (brutalities done in the past) as they are described in the media, is an additional contribute to the perpetuation of this stigma.

Another essential factor that was highlighted is **social pressure**. Participants point out that behaviours are often oriented to what is valued by colleagues instead of what they consider fair behaviours. Note that this factor could be quickly addressed with proper and adequate training so that the professionals are more qualified and able to respond appropriately to challenges.

It is also pinpointed the **difficulty in balancing work and family life**. Participants say that the working schedule and the content of the work quite often impact the quality of family life. Due to the stress experienced at work, some dysfunctional behaviour can occur within family life.

Similarly, it is also noted that poor working conditions, lack of resources, lack of protection, and all the risks involved in the job as a correctional officer contribute to **stress, burnout, and PTSD**.

At last, another factor that was stated was **scarcity and difficulties regarding human resources**, as why CCJ career is not attractive to many professionals. Several participants expressed concern about an aged prison correctional staff, with guards recently retiring. Moreover, most new hirings are not qualified for the job, and no training is provided.

TECHNOLOGICAL FACTORS

Regarding the technological factors that influence career management competencies, the partnership identified some.

First, the massive development of IT, namely social media and the internet, highlighted which have increased speed and low costs. Still, this modern technology requires new competencies for the older staff, such as digital skills. Moreover, some participants noted that prison faces a **lack of proper endowments**, which impacts training once there are not enough computers and no internet connection; therefore, the **staff is imposed to use E-Learning at home**, from their free time.

Nevertheless, BrainLog reported that the participants from Denmark stated that their country is quite advanced in this aspect. For some parts, they are not funded, but even the old prison officers are very digitally skilled compared to other countries. However, it has been self-learning during work processes and development over the years. No digital skills development courses have been offered to the prison staff.

Also, participants say that the acquisition of CCTV, computers and other technological tools is “difference”, as it has both a **deterrent and self-control effect in inmates**. It helps reduce aggression and violence levels because it allows testing in situations of violence or theft, “bringing some justice in here when watching what happened”. The feuds between inmates, for example, are now easier to understand, the environment has become calmer, and there is greater acceptance of the consequences of acts by inmates. In addition, having direct access to the cameras in the office allows controlling what happens among inmates.

With these in mind, the participants also pointed out that research has shown that access to

technology for prisoners can reduce reoffending, and better use of technology for prison officers can free up more of their time for development activities. So, it is generally agreed that investment in prisons to allow more technology that can be used to give both prisoners and prison officers access to more education, training, and development opportunities.

LEGISLATIVE FACTORS

The first aspect pointed out is the **salary**. On the one hand, it continues to be an issue within the criminal justice sector, and there is a perception that better-paid jobs are available outside the prison service with less risk attached. On the other hand, it is considered that frequent alteration in the staff salary leads to insecurity and uncertainty. So, there is an agreement that an increase in pay, and better management of working hours to improve work-life balance, would encourage prison officers to stay in the system.

Similarly, **complicated legislation** makes difficult the implementation of activities. Some participants consider regarding performance reviews that senior staff is not contractually obligated to support junior staff with their professional development. They do not feel that there is any contractual obligation for senior prison staff to offer development, training, and promotional opportunities to more junior staff.

Still, they consider that training and learning are crucial to keep up with the existing laws and provide effective work, training, and learning.

There is also an agreement that there is a **lack of legislation**, leading to an impossibility of normal functioning (ex – unconstitutionality of the legal provisions regarding contexts and evaluation). In addition to this, they believe that there are critical delays in the process of regulation the career status, specially in Portugal.

ENVIRONMENTAL FACTORS

Among the environmental factors identified, the participants stated the **social inclusion and re-education of inmates and the skills necessary for staff/agents** to deal with them. Reference was made to the problem relating to the failure to replace psychiatric hospitals. This leads to the presence of inmates who are challenging to manage (even with mental illness), overcrowding of prisons; high risk of injury and self-harm of prisoners. It would be good to achieve self-sufficiency of the institution as an autonomous microcosm (e.g., inmates contributing with their workforce).

It is also agreed that the content of the work involves a demanding and challenging job, degrading physical conditions of the workplace, and a significant level of stress/burnout. So, prison **staff mental health** is still an issue. Many prison officers may feel they cannot come forward and seek support, as it will be noted on their record and could negatively affect their

chances of promotion. Change in emphasis so mental health support for prison staff is mandatory or considered the norm may help retain good prison officers and encourage more to seek promotion.

In addition to these, it is also said that **training centres** should be modernised, and continuous training should be organised more frequently in those facilities. A concrete and important example is given: female prison officers may find de-escalating violence with male prisoners a more significant challenge; perhaps this limit promotional opportunities for female prison staff? It is suggested that maybe any career development guidance for prison officers must include specific considerations of gender.

CONCLUSION

Following the results of the PESTLE analysis gathered by the partnership, it is evident that the participants from the different countries agree that there are still various problems and issues in what concerns prison systems. **There is also a consensus on the importance and urgency of providing education, training and learning to the correctional staff. It is eminent to reinforce the quality and effectiveness of the staff**, so they are better prepared for this demanding and challenging job. Otherwise, the quality of work will most likely be poor and unsatisfactory, which is dangerous due to the critical role those correctional settings have in society. Re-educating and teaching professionals translate to inmates' progress because they would be more capacitated with adequate skills and competencies to perform their duties better.

4TH STAKEHOLDER CHECK POINT FOR A DACUM VALIDATION OF THE COMPETENCIES PROFILE - AGGREGATE RESULTS

DESCRIPTION OF THE EVENTS

Due to specific motives such as the restrictions imposed to mitigate the ongoing pandemic related to COVID-19, and the obstacle in finding a suitable time frame, considering the workload and shifts held by some prison system professionals, some partners could not manage to implement the DACUM workshops. Therefore, they were compelled to adopt alternative strategies to carry the on with the data collection. In the following table, it is detailed the approaches implemented by each partner:

PARTNER	LOCATION	DATE	DURATION
SNPP	Bucharest, Hotel Union Plaza	13 th October 2021	4,5 hours
Penitenciarul Timisoara	n/a	28 th September 2021 at 9 AM	n/a
IPS	For compelling reasons, such as those mentioned previously, IPS built a DACUM survey on google forms, later disseminated via email to Portuguese prison system professionals.	13 th October 2021	4,5 hours
York Associates	Online	October 2021	n/a
Breman	Zoom platform	5 th and 6 th May 2021	8 hours total (4 hours each day)
BrainLog	For compelling motives, BrainLog had to adopt an alternative strategy and created an online survey through a Google Form to conduct the results for the DACUM report. The survey was disseminated via email to the members of the Danish Prison Union.	The google forms is open until more participants are reached	

Table 2. 4th Stakeholder Checkpoint - Data Collection Strategy by partner

DESCRIPTION OF THE EVENTS

Various stakeholders involved in the course of the DACUM's were invited to the focus groups.

Penitenciarul Timisoara brought together 19 representatives of Timisoara Prison, Arad Prison, Oradea Prison, Educative Center Buzias, Satu Mare Prison, Aiud Prison, International Police, Association- Region 6, Târgu Jiu Prison, Drobeta Turnu Severin Prisona and Timis Probation Service.

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IPS reunited 17 survey collaborators with different positions within the prison system:

- 13 correctional officers
- Two chiefs of guards
- One prison educator
- One psychologist

Ten of the participants are male, and seven are female. The average age is 42,76 years, and the standard deviation is 5,125. Academic background, eight of the respondents completed high school; five hold a bachelor's degree or equivalent; two have a master's degree or equivalent.

The York Associates reunified a Prison officer in a maximum-security facility, with 12 months of service, a Prison officer in a maximum-security facility, with 3.5 years' service, a Recently employed within Probation Service, a Youth Offending Officer in Restorative Justice team, with 6.5 years' service, Experienced teacher and teacher trainer for Career Development course programs for adults, Member of the UK Independent Prisons Monitoring Board, Director of an organisation working on creative learning programmes inside prisons, a Lecturer of Criminology, an University Deputy Dean of School of Education and Social Sciences, formerly Principal Lecturer of Criminology, the Head of Learning & Skills for HM Prison Service, and the checkpoint recorder, currently studying an undergraduate degree in Social Science, provided background materials from research for discussion at this checkpoint.

BrainLog continues collecting data, yet aggregated 6 participants: three of the respondents were prison guards, and the remaining three respondents were one transportation officer, one foreman and managers. The respondents are equally split between male and female, and the total average age is 42,83 years. Four of the respondents have completed a vocational education, one has completed a short-term higher education of two years, and one respondent completed a master's degree or equivalent.

At last, Bremen aggregated professionals with differing job profiles from three different prisons in northern Germany:

- Bremen Prison
- Bremerhaven Prison
- Lübeck Prison

Professionals invited are from the general enforcement service, psychological service, and educating roles with the school for the training of prison officers. Most participants are correctional officers from different departments and prisons, some are educators, and some have a background in human resources within the prison system. The majority of the participants have a professional experience of 10-25 years.

RESULTS

PRISON OFFICERS

CURRENT DUTIES	CURRENT TASKS	COMPETENCIES AND BEHAVIOURAL SKILLS REQUIRED	KNOWLEDGE REQUIRED
Handling/treatment of inmates	Specifically dealing with different languages, religions, and cultures concerning dealing with inmates.	Emotional awareness. Empathy. Alert to signs of bullying or self-harm. Sense of fairness. Resilience. Ensure the safety of the inmates. Perform inmate's searches Know the procedures.	Social skills. Intercultural competencies.
	Actively promoting anti-bullying, prisoner safety, preventing violence, and drug reduction strategies		The clear understanding of process and procedure. Knowledge of prison policies and sanctions
	Escorting inmates outside (e.g., Courts, hospitals, work outside, community activities, transfers, abroad transfers, and extraditions)		Knowledge of the use of weapons and different technical means. Control and restrain techniques
Self-care/ Resilience	Work-Life-Balance/ health and safety/ staying (mentally and physically) healthy	Dynamically react to issues and crises. Dealing with critical and challenging situations	Knowledge about instruments and support structures available in aftercare
Working with prisoners to help them prepare for release	Participation in further training.	Friendly, enthusiastic, cheerful, realistic, managing expectations, aware of inmate needs, able to identify possible issues, professional at all times, active listening skills, assertiveness, positive body language	Be able to identify needs and appropriate routes for support. Knowledge of available services.
	Take an active part in rehabilitation programs, including workshops		
	Establishing positive relationships with prisoners, acting as a positive role model		

CURRENT DUTIES	CURRENT TASKS	COMPETENCIES AND BEHAVIOURAL SKILLS REQUIRED	KNOWLEDGE REQUIRED
Guaranteeing health, safety, rights, and order	Control of security aspects/ensuring a smooth overall process/self-protection as well as protection of prisoners	<p>Organisation. Attention to detail. Diligence. Confidence. Assertiveness. Respectful. Authoritative. Honesty. Empathy.</p> <p>Ability to quickly assess a situation. Decision-making. Working alone and in a team.</p> <p>Communication. Teamwork. Conflict resolution techniques. Crisis situation techniques. Stress management techniques.</p>	<p>Familiarity with prison layout and population. Understanding of process and procedure, knowledge of protocols to correctly perform. Compliance with legislation. Control and restrain techniques. How to work efficiently as part of a team.</p>
	Surveillance, security, control, problem-solving, inmate support, ensuring order and discipline		
	Working within rules to maintain prison order, including responding to incidents where the use of force is required		
	Ensure the integrity of the cells and inmates by checking the facilities and the state of prisoners.		
	Organise the daily activities following the approved daily schedule		
	Observe. Gather information. Inform superiors about inmates' preoccupation and behaviour		
	Solve legal requests of inmates or ensure the pass of information to the competent persons		
Administrative Work	Cooperation with others, ensuring essential services, applications, and statements	Literacy skills honesty, objectiveness, careful (non-emotive) word choices, factual reporting.	Formatting documents under prison policy. Report writing skills. Knowledge about the implementation of requirements in practice
	Completing reports and risk assessments recording incidents		

Table 3. Aggregated results on duties, tasks, competencies, behaviours and knowledge – prison officers

CHALLENGES	FUTURE SKILLS, COMPETENCIES, AND BEHAVIOURS	KNOWLEDGE REQUIRED
Digitalisation / New technologies (online hearings, telemedicine, electronic access, electronic surveillance)	Ability to adapt to changing technology and learn new ways of working	Ongoing training in IT and literacy/numeracy skills, dedicated training for new technologies and systems
Decrease of the quality of the new employees	Willingness to learn, motivation, empathy, confidence, know the procedures, know the law, know the inmates' rights	Training on how to perform duties, the experienced ones should mentor the new ones
Increase of specialised crimes (cybercrimes, terrorism/radicalisation, drugs, organised crime) – modification of the inmates' characteristics	Legislative knowledge. Foreign language. Attention to detail. More knowledge about cultural specifics, value images.	Use of weapons and other intervention means, Time management, Communication, Developing competencies for surveillance
Diversification of culture, language, and religion	Intercultural awareness. Language skills. Awareness of other religions.	Intercultural training. Emotional intelligence training Neurodiversity / SEN training Unconscious bias training
System's inefficiency (lack of resources, lack of motivation of the staff, prison overcrowding, deterioration of facilities). Therefore, doing more with less	Working smarter – considering possible new, more effective ways to carry out tasks	Learn how to take advantage of the available resources
Lack of ethics among staff and inmates.	Ethics Proactivity Willingness to Learn	Training on how to act ethically and how to act regarding the misconduct of staff and inmates.
Lack of discipline among the inmates	Self-Confidence Patience Leadership Self-Control Stress Management Crisis Intervention Skills Conflict Management Skills Emotional Control	Training on how to deal with conflicts and crises. Training on leadership skills. Training on self-control, emotional control, self-confidence, and stress management.
Mental health needs	Understanding of mental health considerations for prisoners. Ability to be empathetic and understanding of mental health issues. More theoretical knowledge about the "correct" way to deal with inmates	Mental health first aid training, detailed understanding of processes for raising concerns about individual inmates.
New methods to combat the phenomenon of introducing prohibited objects in the penitentiary	Awareness of new and different methods of smuggling and new types of prohibited items	Regular communications and updates regarding weapons, drugs, and new smuggling methods. Specific training

Table 4. Aggregated results on challenges, future skills/competencies/behaviours/training – prison officers

PRISON EDUCATORS

CURRENT DUTIES	CURRENT TASKS	COMPETENCIES AND BEHAVIOURAL SKILLS REQUIRED	KNOWLEDGE REQUIRED	CURRENT TRAINING
Counselling	Educational counselling	Counselling abilities. Determination. Empathy.	Counselling knowledge and techniques. Legislative knowledge. Communication. Negotiation. Self-confidence. Assertiveness.	Specific work techniques.
Development of educational programs	Selecting the target groups. Facilitate, monitor, and deliver the programs.	Communication skills. Flexibility.	Knowledge of educational programs. Teaching skills. Leadership.	Specific work techniques.
Assessment	Evaluation of the inmates. Preparation of assessments and reports. Face-to-face service to inmates.	Initiative spirit. Organising skills.	Specific knowledge to be able to carry out an assessment. Minimum of psychological knowledge.	Specific work techniques.
Activity projects	Carrying out activity projects.	Involvement	Knowing the types of activity projects.	Personal development.
Administrative duties	Updating the list of visitors and telephone contacts. Scheduling in-person and video-visits. Drawing up visitor's cards.	Personal effort to develop more effective and efficient Work.	Motivation. Written communication.	-

Table 5. Aggregated results on duties, tasks, competencies, behaviours and knowledge – prison educators

CHALLENGES	FUTURE SKILLS, COMPETENCIES, AND BEHAVIOURS	KNOWLEDGE REQUIRED
Cultural differences – diversified profiles	Flexibility. Capacity to adapt. Know the different needs of the inmates. Empathy.	Reduction of prejudices. Intercultural communication. Conflict-resolution training.
Functional illiteracy – low education levels	Communication skills. Capacity to adapt.	Train on how to deal with different types of inmates and attend to their particularities, (e.g., Elderly inmates, mentally ill inmates.) Specific training on the possibilities of dealing with the inmates and networking with other relevant actors.
Discrepancy between inmates	Know the specificities between types of inmates	
Technology	Duties based on computer tools.	IT training

Table 6. Aggregated results on challenges, future skills/competencies/behaviours/training – prison educators

PROBATION COUNSELLOR

CURRENT DUTIES	CURRENT TASKS	COMPETENCIES AND BEHAVIOURAL SKILLS REQUIRED	KNOWLEDGE REQUIRED	CURRENT TRAINING
Court support	Preparation of the necessary documentation.	Attention, listening skills, skills in summarising information, Risk assessment competencies.	Knowledge in the field of evaluation	Initial training
Support for the social reintegration of released persons	Need identification	Attention, listening skills, skills in summarising information, Risk assessment competencies, needs assessment competencies.	Knowledge in the field of need identification techniques. Assertiveness	Training courses

Table 7. Aggregated results on duties, tasks, competencies, behaviours and knowledge – probation counsellor

CHALLENGES	FUTURE SKILLS, COMPETENCIES, AND BEHAVIOURS	KNOWLEDGE REQUIRED
Division into various compartments within the probation service	Specific skills and tasks depending on the specialisation.	Reduction of prejudices. Intercultural communication. Conflict-resolution training.
Adapting the intervention programme to new technologies	Minimum knowledge in the IT field. Learning new programs.	IT training
Adaptation to multiculturalism	Flexibility. Adaptation.	Learn the needs and specificities of different cultures.

Table 8. Aggregated results on challenges, future skills/competencies/behaviours/training – probation counsellor

PSYCHOLOGISTS

CURRENT DUTIES	CURRENT TASKS	COMPETENCIES AND BEHAVIOURAL SKILLS REQUIRED	KNOWLEDGE REQUIRED	CURRENT TRAINING
Psychological assessment	Psychological assess and evaluate the inmates. Follow-up.	Self-confidence. Pro-activity. Ethics. Respect. Crisis intervention skills.	Knowledge in the psychological field and assessments	n/a
Psychosocial support	Psychological intervention.	Emotional control. Patience.	Knowledge in the psychological field.	n/a

Table 9. Aggregated results on duties, tasks, competencies, behaviours and knowledge – psychologists

CHALLENGES	FUTURE SKILLS, COMPETENCIES, AND BEHAVIOURS	KNOWLEDGE REQUIRED
Rigid system and a lot of bureaucracy	Learn how to deal with few resources	Motivation training Organisation Smart Work

Table 10. Aggregated results on challenges, future skills/competencies/behaviours/training - psychologists

MAIN FINDINGS

Through the analysis of the results previously mentioned, it gets clear that the areas highly identified as in need to be developed through training are transversal regardless of the job role or the country, which are particularly:

Figure 1. Areas of training identified

On the subject of mental health awareness and strategies, the participants emphasise two different needs in this respect:

- 1) Deal with inmates who have mental illness.
- 2) Mental health in correctional staff.

Concerning the first topic, there is a significant number of inmates with mental health issues. Likewise, the correctional staff considers it crucial to be capable of understanding mental health considerations to deal better with the inmates and to respond more effectively to their needs. Therefore, it would be beneficial for the collaborators to have frequent training, such as: awareness/understanding mental health, mental health first aid, techniques/strategies to deal with mentally ill inmates, and (but not limited) alert to signs of self-harm.

Concerning the second topic, working in prisons, as stated by the participants, can be very demotivating and stressful, potentially leading to burnout, PTSD, anxiety, among other problems. Similarly, most participants say they struggle in balancing work issues with family and personal time. Above these, it is reported that it is not provided training to the staff on

mental health issues. Hence, it is essential to offer training to capacitate them to deal with those problems, namely conscientiousness about the importance of taking care of mental health, alert signs, techniques/strategies, coping with stress and challenging situations, and demystifying psychotherapy.

The need for **IT training** is shared by the diverse participants, due to the significant increase in digitalisation. Some partners identified that sometimes training is provided to address this, yet other partners reported that no training is provided. For both cases, more training is required, as it is found a generalised concern of the prison staff to keep up with the technological demands, particularly the older staff. In fact, it is noted that **digital skills are required regardless of the job position**, which enforces the need for the training. Simultaneously, as digital skills are in need, modern technology is valued and needed to enhance and support the tasks and duties. So, it is required to train and promote the skills of the staff in this respect.

The enhancement of specific soft skills is noteworthy because most of them are shared to perform tasks and duties successfully, no matter the job role within the prison. These are:

Figure 2. Soft skills identified as in need of training

All these skills are essential to work in prison, and all of them can be promoted and developed; they are not static aspects. Therefore, training can make a difference to capacitate the participants to be better professionals.

It is also pointed out the importance to own **knowledge of important procedures**. It is easy to recognise that every professional needs to know what they are doing and understand the procedures to perform well. The participants highlight specific procedures, such as:

Figure 3. Specific procedures identified as in need of training

All these competencies are benefits to be promoted through formal training. Still, there are many advantages if new professionals could learn from the experience and practical knowledge of professionals who perform their job for longer. No one better than people who do it every day to teach and coach on how to perform specific procedures.

Many participants report the difficulties they face in dealing with the specificities between inmates (culture, language, age, and religion) – different inmates require different approaches and concerns. So, prison staff agree that they need training on social skills, intercultural competencies, and awareness of other religions. Also, age requires training on dealing with elderly inmates since they require specific concerns.

Training for female prison staff was also pointed out because they may find more challenges and limited promotional opportunities for female prison staff. So, it is suggested that careers development guidance for prison officers must include specific considerations of gender.

At last, participants find it important to know and deal with the increase of specialised crimes, such as cybercrimes, terrorism/radicalisation, drugs, or organised crime, leading to modifying the inmates' characteristics. The staff must keep updated on the characteristics of the new groups of offenders that are arising. Therefore, they must acquire competencies on how to deal effectively with the inmates, and for this, they need to know these groups. There is another important aspect considering specialised crimes, particularly to the Italian prisons, which have mafia linked inmates, as the Italian participants reported difficulties in dealing with them. These types of criminals require a precise approach because they have particular characteristics, needs and attributes that must be considered when dealing with them. In line with these, dealing with mafia offenders is critical to Italian prison workers.

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APPENDIXES

APPENDIX 1. CLASSIFICATION OF COMPETENCIES

According to the EQF - European Qualification Framework - (European Commission, 2017), Competence is ‘the proven ability to use knowledge, skills and personal, social and/ or methodological skills, work or study situations, and professional and personal development. Hence, it englobes the following three elements: knowledge, skills, and attitudes. The approach adopted is consistent with this definition, encompassing social and personal abilities. Moreover, once competencies are holistic units that express complex behaviours, competence areas are a set of competencies clustered according to specific criteria.

For the structure of the CorrectionCareers, will be used the European e-Competence Framework and its four dimensions (www.ecompetences.eu):

DIMENSION 1	Eight competence areas: Mental Health Literacy, Digital Skills, Soft Skills, Hard Skills, Inmates Diversity Management, Managing Inmates convicted with New Organised Crimes, Gender Mainstreaming Awareness.
DIMENSION 2	A set of reference Competencies for each area, with a generic description for each. Each Competence will have a definition.
DIMENSION 3	Proficiency levels of each Competence (related to EQF): from e-1 to e-5, related to EQF levels 3-8.
DIMENSION 4	Samples of knowledge and skills relate to Competencies in dimension 2. They are provided to add value and context.

This structure is based on competence areas (dimension 1) and competencies (dimension 2) instead of job profiles, providing a more flexible approach and fostering local personalisation. Within dimension 1, “Competence areas”, concepts are more general and fit different professional profiles considered relevant to the community professionals. In dimension 2: “Competencies”, descriptors are specific and directly related to community CCJ4C contexts. Dimension 3 provides level assignments appropriate to each Competence, and dimension 4 provides short sample specifications of knowledge and skills, but the list is not exhaustive.

CORRECTION CAREERS - PROFICIENCY LEVELS

5

KNOWLEDGE

Knowledge at the most advanced frontier of a field of work or study and the interface between areas.

SKILLS

The most advanced and specialised skills and techniques, including synthesis and evaluation, are required to solve critical research problems and/or innovation and extend and refine existing knowledge or professional practice.

COMPETENCIES

Demonstrate substantial authority, innovation, autonomy, scholarly and professional integrity, and sustained commitment to developing new ideas or processes at the forefront of work or study contexts, including research.

EQF LEVELS

8

EQF LEVELS

7

KNOWLEDGE

Knowledge at the most advanced frontier of a field of work or study and the interface between areas.

SKILLS

The most advanced and specialised skills and techniques, including synthesis and evaluation, are required to solve critical research problems and/or innovation and extend and refine existing knowledge or professional practice.

COMPETENCIES

Demonstrate substantial authority, innovation, autonomy, scholarly and professional integrity, and sustained commitment to developing new ideas or processes at the forefront of work or study contexts, including research.

CORRECTION CAREERS - PROFICIENCY LEVELS

4

KNOWLEDGE

Advanced knowledge of a field of work or study involving a critical understanding of theories and principles.

SKILLS

Advanced skills, demonstrating mastery and innovation, required to solve complex and unpredictable problems in a specialised field of work and/or research.

COMPETENCIES

Manage complex technical or professional activities or projects, take responsibility for decision-making in unpredictable work or study contexts, and manage individual and group professional development.

EQF LEVELS

6

EQF LEVELS

5

KNOWLEDGE

Comprehensive, specialised, factual, and theoretical knowledge within a field of work or study and an awareness of that knowledge's boundaries.

SKILLS

A comprehensive range of cognitive and practical skills is required to develop creative solutions to abstract problems.

COMPETENCIES

Exercise management and supervision in work or training activities where there is unpredictable change; review and develop the performance of self and others.

CORRECTION CAREERS - PROFICIENCY LEVELS **3**

KNOWLEDGE

Factual and theoretical knowledge in broad contexts within a field of work or study.

SKILLS

A range of cognitive and practical skills is required to generate solutions to specific problems in a field of work or study.

COMPETENCIES

Exercise self-management within the guidelines of work or study contexts that are usually predictable but are subject to change; supervise routine work and take responsibility for evaluating and improving work or study activities.

EQF LEVELS

4

KNOWLEDGE

Knowledge of facts, principles, processes and general concepts in a field of work or study.

SKILLS

A range of cognitive and practical skills is required to accomplish tasks and solve problems by selecting and applying basic methods, tools, materials, and information.

COMPETENCIES

Take responsibility for completing tasks in work or study; adapt own behaviour to circumstances in solving problems.

EQF LEVELS

3

CORRECTION CAREERS - PROFICIENCY LEVELS **2**

KNOWLEDGE

Advanced knowledge of a field of work or study involving a critical understanding of theories and principles.

SKILLS

Advanced skills, demonstrating mastery and innovation, required to solve complex and unpredictable problems in a specialised field of work and/or research.

COMPETENCIES

Manage complex technical or professional activities or projects, take responsibility for decision-making in unpredictable work or study contexts, and manage individual and group professional development.

EQF LEVELS

2

CORRECTION CAREERS - PROFICIENCY LEVELS **1**

KNOWLEDGE

Basic general knowledge

SKILLS

Basic skills required to carry out simple tasks

COMPETENCIES

Work or study under direct supervision in a structured context

EQF LEVELS

1

Partners identified samples of knowledge and skills included in each Competence identified and defined in dimensions 2 and 3—accordingly, dimension 4 details examples of core elements/components related to the competency contents. This dimension’s main aim is to provide added value and context to the framework users, and it is not intended to be exhaustive.

Definitions used in the CCJ4C:

- **Knowledge** represents the “set of know-what” (e.g., mediation tools...) and can be described by operational descriptions.
- **Skill** is the “ability to carry out managerial or technical tasks”. Managerial and technical skills are components of competencies and specify some core abilities that form Competence.

The partnership agreed to build this tool to be an operational tool for the lifelong learning process of correctional justice system professionals and the basis for structured educational development in training providers.

The following dimensions were developed according to Bloom’s Taxonomy approach of Educational Objectives for the Cognitive Domain (Anderson & Krathwohl (2001):

1. Knowledge;
2. Comprehension;
3. Application;
4. Analysis;
5. Synthesis;
6. Evaluation.

This approach allows differentiation between **cognitive skill levels** and **calls attention to learning objectives** that require higher levels of cognitive skills, **leading to deeper learning and transfer of knowledge and skills to a greater variety of tasks and contexts.**

COGNITIVE LEVEL	ILLUSTRATIVE VERBS	DEFINITIONS
KNOWLEDGE	arrange, define, describe, duplicate, identify, label, list, match, memorise, name, order, outline, recognise, relate, recall, repeat, reproduce, select, state	remembering previously learned information
COMPREHENSION	classify, convert, defend, discuss, distinguish, estimate, explain, express, extend, generalise, give an example(s), identify, indicate, infer, locate, paraphrase, predict, recognise, rewrite, report, restate, review, select, summarise, translate	grasping the meaning of information

COGNITIVE LEVEL	ILLUSTRATIVE VERBS	DEFINITIONS
APPLICATION	apply, change, choose, compute, demonstrate, discover, dramatise, employ, illustrate, interpret, manipulate, modify, operate, practice, predict, prepare, produce, relate schedule, show, sketch, solve, use, write	applying knowledge to actual situations
ANALYSIS	analyse, appraise, breakdown, calculate, categorise, classify, compare, contrast, criticise, derive, diagram, differentiate, discriminate, distinguish, examine, experiment, identify, illustrate, infer, interpret, model, outline, point out, question, relate, select, separate, subdivide, test	breaking down objects or ideas into simpler parts and seeing how the aspects relate and are organised
SYNTHESIS	arrange, assemble, categorise, collect, combine, comply, compose, construct, create, design, develop, devise, explain, formulate, generate, plan, prepare, propose, rearrange, reconstruct, relate, reorganise, revise, rewrite, set up, summarise, synthesise, tell, write	mixing component ideas into a new whole
EVALUATION	appraise, argue, assess, attach, choose, compare, conclude, contrast, defend, describe, discriminate, estimate, evaluate, explain, judge, justify, interpret, relate, predict, rate, select, summarise, support, value	Making judgements based on internal evidence or external criteria

The CCJ4C Consortium is aware of the challenges and opportunities involved in building a common European framework. Considering that the topic of the project is singular, and the features are context-driven, the work developed is open to improvements and upgrades to other areas of competency or competencies.

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